

The Assessment of Female Breast Cancer Tumors Using Some Biomarkers in Attendees of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Breast cancer has remained a major public health issue globally but predominantly affects women in developing nations. The overall survival rate of Nigerian women with breast cancer is low and patients with early breast cancer tend to have better survival than those with advanced disease and pathology. These changes are leading to revisions in the management of the disease with a positive impact on prognosis. The current research was done to describe the epidemiological and histopathological features of breast cancer amongst females attending the Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. In this retrospective study, 178 breast specimens were used, spanning from 2010 to 2022. Results presented an age at diagnosis lower to the Western population and invasive ductal carcinoma as the main histological type. In this study, the prevalence of breast cancer amongst females attending Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria was analyzed using Hematoxylin and Eosin staining techniques on breast cancer samples collected over the study period. The pathophysiology of breast cancer is not very clear; however, some risk factors are. While some common risk factors are advancing age and the female gender, genetic mutations—namely BRCA 1 and 2—account for only about 10% of breast cancers. The role played by biomarkers, such as estrogen receptors, progesterone receptors, and human epidermal growth factor receptors, in the detection and management of patients with breast cancer. Human breast cancer is known to be dependent on sexual hormones for its growth, as it is derived from breast tissue that normally responds to endogenous hormones. Despite improvements in early detection and therapy, Breast Cancer remains one of the major burdens to healthcare systems and societies.

Introduction

Breast cancer is one of the leading health disorders in the world. It is one of the most common malignancies affecting millions of women every year [1]. Breast cancers are divided into three types: invasive,

noninvasive, and lobular carcinomas [2]. The International Breast Cancer Study Group categorized the disease into three subtypes according to the response: receptor-positive responsive, response uncertain, and nonresponsive. International Agency

More Information

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Keywords:

Female Breast cancer, Assessment, Human Epidermal Growth Factor receptor 2 (her2), Estrogen receptors (Er), Progesterone receptors (Pr), Molecular subtypes, cytokeratin 5/6.

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Research on Cancer (IARC) counted 28,380 new cases of breast cancer in Nigeria in 2020 alone, accounting for 22.7 percent of new cancers and becoming the deadliest cancer type in Nigeria [3]. The pathophysiology of breast cancer is not very clear; however, some risk factors are. While some common risk factors are advancing age and the female gender, genetic mutations—namely BRCA 1 and 2—account for only about 10% of breast cancers. Other factors that increase risk also include ductal carcinoma in situ, high body mass index, early menarche, late menopause, and use of postmenopausal hormone therapy [4]. Biomarkers, such as estrogen receptors, progesterone receptors, and human epidermal growth factor receptors, play a role in the detection and management of patients with breast cancer [5]. BRCA1/2 mutation testing in risk assessment in families showing a high prevalence of both breast and ovarian cancers. Multi-analyte profiles, including uPA/PAI-1 or Oncotype DX, permit prognosis to be determined and lymph node-negative patients to be identified who may be spared adjuvant chemotherapy [6]. Human breast cancer is known to be dependent on sexual hormones for its growth, as it is derived from breast tissue that normally responds to endogenous hormones [7]. Thus, endocrine therapy rapidly became a standard in the treatment of breast cancer. Only one-third of patients responded to endocrine therapy [8]. An estrogen receptor was postulated to exist, but only about 8% of ER-negative tumors had an objective response to endocrine treatment [9]. Despite improvements in early detection and therapy, Breast Cancer remains one of the major burdens to healthcare systems and societies. There is an actual need for accurate and reliable biomarkers to improve diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment selection [10]. This work, therefore, evaluated the incidence of female breast cancer tumors using some biomarkers such as Estrogen, Progesterone, and Her2 among females attending the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, using the Hematoxylin and Eosin Staining Technique on breast cancer samples only, with a study period.

Materials and Methods

Study Area and Site

Bayelsa State was formed on October 1, 1996, from the previous River State. There are eight (8) local government areas, with the capital at Yenagoa metropolis [11]. The 2006 census estimated the state population to be 1,704, 515 people, with 874, 084 males and 830, 432 females. The state is a coastal region with mangrove swamps, dense rainforest, and a short dry season from November to March. The Atlantic Ocean borders the west and south, the neighboring states of Rivers border the east, and Delta borders the north. It has four primary cultural ethnic groups: Izon, Nembe, Ogbia, and Epie-Attisa, each with its own

language [12]. Most people in this area identify as Christians, with only a handful practicing traditional religions. According to [13], Bayelsa State suffers greatly from the country's health indicator ranking of 187th out of 191 countries in the world reported in 2000. Farming, fishing, palm oil milling, logging, tapping palm wine, and producing local gin are the most common occupations. The state has a land mass of 12,110 square kilometers, with water covering more than three-quarters of the area. The land topography is two (2) meters below sea level. It is located at latitudes 4o15N and 5O23S, and longitudes 5O22 and 6O5 East of the equator. Bayelsa State is Nigeria's second-largest crude oil producer, with the country's largest gas reserves and oil wells. Hematoxylin and Eosin, as well as microtomy procedures, were performed at the Federal Medical Center Bayelsa State, Yenagoa Bayelsa State.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics and research committees of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Study population

A retrospective assessment of all Female breast cancer tumors from 2010 to 2022 in the institution's Histopathology Laboratory served as the study samples.

Research design

The research was a retrospective and a cross-sectional study. Therefore, the data on the relationship between tumor markers and primary breast cancer and other variables of interest, as they exist in our defined population, was collected at a single point in time within the periods of ten years review. This model was by [14].

Sample Size Determination and Sample Selection

The formula of [15] was used to determine the sample size for the study. Therefore, applying the formula $N = Z^2pq/d^2$ Where:

N = the calculated sample size (for a population greater than 10,000)

Z = the standard (alpha) normal deviation usually set at 1.96 which corresponds to a 95% confidence level

p = the disease prevalence in the population study.

$sq = 1.0 - p$

d = degree of accuracy (precision) desired usually set at 0.05

$N = 187$ based on a reported prevalence of 14.7%

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All previously diagnosed breast cancer tissue blocks between 2010-2022 with adequate information such as the patient's age, clinical details, and available tissue mass or blocks were selected, while tissue blocks with another form of malignancy and dates above and below the time frame were excluded.

Sampling Methods

The convenience sampling method was used to select the formalin fixed paraffin embedded breast cancer tissue blocks (2010 – 2022) from the histopathology archives of the center. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling that involves the samples drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand [16].

Laboratory Procedure

Preparation of Breast Cancer Tissues

The method of [17] was adopted in preparing the breast tissues. The tissue block selected was sectioned into four (4) microns using a rotary microtome. The serial sections were floated in a water bath at a temperature of 55°C for 2 min. The floated sections were picked using labeled grease-free frosted end slides. Seventy-one slides were submitted for Ehrlich’s hematoxylin and eosin staining.

Haematoxylin and Eosin Staining (Breast Tissues)

Ehrlich’s hematoxylin and Eosin method was used for histological studies by [17]. The slides were stained and read to confirm the previous diagnosis. Primary histopathological evaluation was made on 5 µm thick sections stained with usual Hematoxylin– Eosin. The classification was made according to WHO’s criteria, and the majority (n = 19) of the cases were invasive ductal carcinoma, two were invasive papillary carcinomas and one was mucinous carcinoma. The

Scarff–Bloom–Richardson system, which is the modified Elston–Ellis’s system was used in grading the invasive ductal carcinoma

Principle

The principle of reaction is based on the chemical theory of dye; where the acidic component of the tissue is stained by the basic dye (hematoxylin) blue and the basic component (cytoplasm) is stained by the acidic dye (Eosin) pink.

Procedure

The breast tissues were sectioned using rotary microtomes into serial sections and stained. The slide sections were dewaxed and hydrated in water, drained, and transferred to hematoxylin solution (primary stain) for 20 min until the nuclei stained blue. Rinse in water and immediately subject to two seconds differentiation using 1% acid alcohol, rinse to stop the reaction, and blue in Scot’s tap water to restore the nuclear stain. Dehydrate in three changes of alcohol (70%, 95%, Absolute) and stain in 1% Eosin (cytoplasmic stain) dehydrate in two changes of alcohol (95% and Absolute) and clear in xylene and mount in DPX.

Statistical Analysis

The raw data was coded in a spreadsheet for each analysis on the statistical software package Graph Pad Prism 5 (Graphed Software Inc., 2014). Data was presented in percentages.

RESULT

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic of Breast Disease among Subjects Studied

Variables	No. Observed	Percentage
Tumor type		
Malignant	71	37.9
Malignant	116	62.1
Gender		
Male case	4	2.2
Female cases	183	97.8
Histologic type		
Ductal carcinoma	68	95.8
Lobular carcinoma	3	4.2
Anatomical position		
Right breast	61	33.5
Left breast	63	34.5
Bilateral	5	26.7
No documentation	58	31.0

Table 1 summarizes the selected variable among breast cancer patients examined. Malignant breast cancer accounted for 37.9% of all breast disorders analyzed throughout the period, while benign lesions accounted for 62.1%. The majority of malignant lesions, 95.8%, were ductal carcinoma; on the other hand, lobular

carcinoma accounted for only 4.2%. The data showed that 33.5% of the lesions were in the right breast, 34.5% were in the left breast; 26.7% were bilateral. Thirty-one percent of the cases had poorly documented clinical information.

Table 2: Tumor Markers over Expression among Subjects Studied

Tumor markers	No examined	Overexpression	Prevalence (%)
Estrogens (ER)	71	Positive score 46 +2= 12 +3= 18 Negative score 25	65.0 25.0 40.0 35.0
Progesterone (PR)	71	Positive score 50 + 2=10 + 3=25 Negative score 15	70.0 20.0 50.0 30.0
EGF2	71	Positive score 28 +2= 4 +3=7 Negative score 17	40.0 15.0 25.0 60.0
Cytokeratin 5/6	71	11	15.0

Table 2. Percentages of expressed breast hormone receptors and oncogenes: Estrogen receptor positive versus negativity as 65:35%, progesterone 70:30%,

epidermal growth factor-2 15:0%, 25% equivocal, and Ck5/6 15.0%.

Figure 1: H&E

Figure 2: ER+

Figure 3: PR+

Figure 4: HER2+

Discussion

Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in females in developed countries, affecting one in

every eight women in the United States [1]. Developing countries do not remain behind. In this study, males accounted for 2.2% of total cases and 97.8% were

female. Male breast cancer patients had a lower survival rate than female breast cancer patients, according to most previous research [18]. The average age at presentation was 48.21 years, with 59.1% of patients being under 50 years [19]. Following [20], the left breast was more commonly affected than the right. The response of these tumors to hormone therapy is critical to breast care and patient survival. Racial disparities in breast cancer survival between and within countries are associated with early detection, access to diagnosis and treatment, cultural differences in lifestyle behaviors, socioeconomic factors, and differences in breast cancer biology [21]. Her-2/neu positivity was found to be 40% in this study, with reports from other parts of Nigeria showing 30.8%, 22.0%, 11.4%, and 20.8%. The immunopositivity of breast cancer for Her-2/neu among participants was 15.0%, consistent with earlier studies in Nigeria. The current study's value falls between 10 to 52%, as reported in numerous studies globally.

Further research is needed to determine the true incidence of Her-2/neu status in the overall Bayelsa State population. Variations in methods, pre-analytical factors, and the use of automated equipment and tissue fixation could all contribute to these prevalence disparities [22]. The therapeutic role of estrogen receptors (ERs) and progesterone receptors (PRs) in breast carcinomas is well documented. In a South African public hospital investigation, 63% of tumors among black breast cancer patients were ER-positive [23]. The prognostic significance of PR positivity in the absence of ER is debatable, with some studies claiming that positive PR, even in the absence of ER, indicates a patient group more receptive to hormone therapy [24]. In this study, information on receptor status was available in 71 cases, with 50% being ER-positive, 31.3% being PR positive, 44% being both ER and PR positive, 19% being ER-positive and PR negative, and 2.9% being ER negative and PR positive. As a result, our patients have much higher receptor positivity than studies conducted in the rest of Asia.

Conclusion

The frequency of molecular subtypes of breast cancer varies geographically, probably due to technical differences in tissue fixation, staining methods, and reporting standards or the biological heterogeneity of African breast cancers under genetic and environmental factors in this study.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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